

1 **Ivermectin as a Novel Malaria Control Tool: Getting Ahead of the Resistance Curse**

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21 **Abstract**

22 Reduction in malaria clinical cases is strongly dependent on the ability to prevent *Anopheles*
23 infectious bites. Vector control strategies using long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual
24 spraying with insecticides have contributed to significantly reduce the incidence of malaria in
25 many endemic countries, especially in the Sub-Saharan region. However, global progress in
26 reducing malaria cases has plateaued since 2015 mostly due to the increased insecticide
27 resistance and behavioral changes in *Anopheles* vectors. Additional control strategies are thus
28 required to further reduce the burden of malaria and contain the spread of resistant and invasive
29 *Anopheles* vectors. The use of endectocides such as ivermectin as an additional malaria control
30 tool is now receiving increased attention, driven by its different mode of action compared to
31 insecticides used so far and its excellent safety record for humans. In this opinion article, we
32 discuss the advantages and disadvantages of using ivermectin for malaria control with a focus on
33 the risk of selecting ivermectin resistance in malaria vectors. We also highlight the importance of
34 understanding how ivermectin resistance could develop in mosquitoes and what its underlying
35 mechanisms and associated molecular markers are, and propose a research agenda to manage this
36 phenomenon.

37 **Keywords:** Malaria; Mass Drug Administration; residual transmission; Ivermectin resistance;
38 *Anopheles*

39 **The need for alternative vector control strategies**

40 Preventing *Anopheles* mosquito bites is essential for controlling malaria infection. In areas where
41 the main malaria vector species are endophagic (*i.e.* prefer to bite indoors), endophilic (*i.e.* prefer
42 to rest indoors) and anthropophilic (*i.e.* prefer to feed on humans), the use of long-lasting

43 insecticidal nets (LLINs) and indoor residual spraying (IRS) with insecticides have been shown
44 to be particularly effective. These two interventions take advantage of the behavior of major
45 malaria vectors, and have become the pillars of malaria control (1,2). In the context of renewed
46 efforts against malaria, an estimated 663 million cases were averted between 2000 and 2015, of
47 which 68% were attributed to the use of LLINs and 10% to IRS (3). This remarkable reduction in
48 the burden of malaria was achieved thanks to a strong multilateral commitment and an increased
49 international financing effort for malaria control (4). This significant public health achievement
50 sparked enthusiasm to continue the control efforts with the goal of elimination in areas where
51 LLINs and IRS were highly successful.

52 However, the 2021 world malaria report (5) indicates that global progress in reducing malaria
53 cases has stalled since 2015, with only <2% of decline in malaria incidence between 2015 and
54 2020, and even an increase in several countries including Eritrea, Namibia, Angola, Botswana,
55 Burundi, the Comoros and Madagascar. The development of effective insecticide-based vector
56 control strategies is increasingly challenging because of the widespread emergence of insecticide
57 resistance in malaria vectors. Until 2017, pyrethroids were the only class of insecticides
58 recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) for impregnating mosquito nets (6).
59 This large-scale use of pyrethroids in public health in addition to their use in agriculture has
60 selected among mosquito populations, individuals bearing resistance mechanisms such as target
61 site mutations, cuticular resistance, and metabolic resistance (7–11). Insecticide resistance has
62 become so widespread across malaria endemic countries that it became obvious to the scientific
63 community that LLINs and IRS alone would not be sufficient to reach elimination even if they
64 were efficiently implemented by malaria control programs (12).

65 Moreover, while insecticide resistance in mosquitoes is primarily seen as the capacity to survive
66 the exposure to established lethal concentrations, behavioral changes leading to reduced exposure
67 or full avoidance can also significantly hamper insecticide efficacy. These behavioral changes
68 include a shift in resting (*i.e.* exophily) and feeding preferences (*i.e.* exophagy and zoophagy)
69 (13–19), early (before dusk) or late (after dawn) biting activities (13,18,20,21) and daytime biting
70 activities (22) as well as early exit from households after feeding (23). These changes occurred in
71 presence of strong selective pressure with over two billion nets delivered in 2020 (24) and
72 involved either ecological shifts in vector species composition (25–28) or evolutionary
73 adaptations of vector species aggressive behaviors (29) that are increasingly documented in
74 malaria endemic countries. These departures from canonical behaviors together with
75 physiological resistance represent loopholes in the effectiveness of the current integrated vector
76 control strategy that exclusively relies on LLINs and IRS. The direct consequence of these
77 changes in the persistence of malaria transmission (30,31).

78 This persistence of malaria transmission despite efficient use of current vector control strategies
79 is termed residual transmission. This phenomenon defines the limits of what is achievable with
80 currently available vector control tools and threatens the achievement of malaria elimination
81 goals. Additional, complementary strategies to LLINs and/or IRS are urgently required to further
82 reduce the burden of malaria and contain the spread of physiologically and/or behaviorally
83 resistant as well as invasive vectors (32–34).

84 **Ivermectin as a complementary tool to control malaria**

85 The use of endectocides to increase the mortality rate of female mosquitoes before they can
86 transmit the malaria parasite is a promising approach to reduce malaria transmission (35).
87 Endectocides are chemicals that were first widely used in the livestock industry to control

88 endoparasites (*i.e.* intestinal nematodes) and ectoparasites (*i.e.* blood-feeding arthropods) (36).
89 Several endectocide drugs are effective against a wide range of endo- and ectoparasites in
90 animals as well as in humans, including the avermectins (abamectin, doramectin, eprinomectin,
91 and ivermectin) and the milbemycins (milbemectin, moxidectin, nemadectin) (37). Ivermectin
92 was the first endectocide used in humans, and it has been licensed since 1987 as a microfilaricide
93 for the control of human endemic helminthiases (onchocerciasis and lymphatic filariasis) through
94 mass drug administration (MDA) (38,39). Interestingly, malaria vectors have been shown to be
95 sensitive to therapeutic doses of ivermectin when feeding on treated people or animals (40–43).
96 Thus, this molecule could be considered as an “systemic insecticide” directly distributed by
97 treated vertebrate hosts, including humans (**Figure 1**).

98 **Figure 1:** Schematic representation of the use of ivermectin to combat malaria in a One Health
99 approach and its potential ecological impacts. *Residual malaria transmission could be addressed*
100 *by administering ivermectin to livestock (A) and/or to human (B) through MDAs. In addition of*
101 *targeting malaria mosquitoes and animal ectoparasites, the drug will improve human and animal*

102 *health by targeting intestinal parasites. However, the drug can accumulate in animal meat and*
103 *milk [i] making them temporarily unfit for human consumption. Ivermectin and its metabolites*
104 *are mainly excreted through feces. Fecal residues of ivermectin in cattle dung may affect dung-*
105 *dwelling insects such as dung beetles and flies, [ii] leading to less amended soils. Some portions*
106 *can also contaminate waterbodies and affect invertebrate and aquatic organisms [iii]. The*
107 *repeated use of ivermectin has resulted in the spread of resistance mechanisms due to the strong*
108 *selective pressure on herd parasites [iv], a process that can likely occurs in human parasites and*
109 *mosquito populations (larva and adults) [v].*

110 ***Some advantages***

111 Unlike current insecticides used on LLINs or for IRS that mostly target the voltage-gated sodium
112 channels, ivermectin binds to the glutamate-gated chloride channels (GluCl_s) which regulate the
113 passage of chloride ions into and out of the invertebrate neuronal or muscular cells. By hyper-
114 activating the channels, ivermectin induces muscle paralysis and flaccid death (44). GluCl_s are
115 not present in vertebrates, and although cross reaction with GABA-gated chloride channels is
116 possible, the latter are present in the central nervous system and protected by the blood brain
117 barrier that actively pumps out xenobiotics, hence ivermectin's excellent safety track record in
118 humans and livestock (45). Carried by the host himself, ivermectin administered through MDAs
119 to humans and/or animals will likely target malaria vectors regardless of their temporal or spatial
120 feeding behavior (**Figure 1**). Ivermectin has the potential to decrease malaria transmission by
121 reducing the survival as well as the fecundity of malaria vector mosquitoes (reviewed by (46,47))
122 and the impact could be greater in highly seasonal (about four months) and seasonal malaria
123 transmission settings. Indeed, a modeling study based on epidemiological data from Senegal,
124 Liberia and Burkina Faso has predicted that ivermectin MDA in human administered in three

125 monthly rounds, each with three consecutive daily doses of 300 µg/kg and reaching 70%
126 coverage could reduce malaria clinical incidence by 71% and prevalence by 34% in highly
127 seasonal moderate transmission settings (48). The authors also predict that adding ivermectin
128 MDA to seasonal malaria chemoprevention in these settings would reduce clinical incidence by
129 an additional 77% in children younger than 5 years compared with seasonal malaria
130 chemoprevention alone (48). Various trials are evaluating ivermectin MDA as a complementary
131 malaria vector control tool (**Table 1**). All these studies will bring an in-depth insight of the
132 potential of ivermectin to become a valuable tool to be added in the malaria control toolbox.

133 Aside its impact on adult *Anopheles* survival and fecundity, ivermectin present in larval habitats
134 can also reduce the survival of larvae of *An. gambiae s.l.* (49). This suggests that ivermectin that
135 is excreted in the environment after MDA to humans or animals could indirectly affect malaria
136 vector populations, and thereby malaria transmission. In addition to its toxicity for malaria
137 vectors, ivermectin, even at sub-lethal concentrations, may inhibit the sporogony of *P. falciparum*
138 and *P. vivax* in malaria vectors (50,51). Additional benefits may come from the effect of
139 ivermectin on other endo- and ectoparasites (52,53); MDA of ivermectin for malaria could reduce
140 the burden of intestinal and ectoparasites (54).

141

142 **Table 1:** Previous and ongoing trials assessing the efficacy of ivermectin as a complementary malaria control tool

Study name	Lead researchers	Country	Study design	Number of participants	Dose	Regimen	MDA frequency	Treated host	Study period
REACT I	Cedric Pennetier Roch Dabiré	Burkina Faso	cRCT	2,609	200µg/kg	Single dose	Every 4 weeks for 4 consecutive months	Livestock	2016-2018
RIMDAMAL I	Brian Foy and Roch Dabiré	Burkina Faso	cRCT	2,712	150-200µg/kg	Single dose	Every 3 weeks for 4 consecutive months	Human	2014-2016
RIMDAMAL II	Brian Foy and Roch Dabiré	Burkina Faso	cRCT	4,088	300µg/kg	X 3 consecutive days	X 4 consecutive months	Human	2018-2023
ANNIVERMATE	Karine Mouline	Burkina Faso	Experimental	8	1.2 mg/kg (<i>long-acting formulation</i>)	Single dose	Once	Livestock	2018-2020
MATAMAL	Anna Last	Guinea-Bissau	cRCT	24,000	300µg/kg + DHA-P	X 3 consecutive days	X 3 consecutive months	Human	2019-2022
IVERMECTIN MDA	Jetsumon Prachumsri	Thailand	cRCT	6,356	400µg/kg	Single dose	X 3 consecutive months	Human	2017-2023
BOHEMIA	Regina Rabinovich and Carlos Chaccour	Mozambique and Kenya	cRCT	20,000-22,000	400µg/kg	Single dose	X 3 consecutive months	Human and/or livestock	2019-2023
IMPACT	Karine Mouline	Burkina Faso	Experimental	36	0.6-1.5mg/kg (<i>long-acting formulation</i>)	Single dose	Once	Livestock	2020-2023
MASSIV	Umberto D'alessandro	The Gambia	cRCT	4,939	300-400µg/kg + DHA-P	X 3 consecutive days	X 3 consecutive months	Human	2017-2020

143 cRCT= cluster Randomized Controlled Trial; DHA-P = Di-Hydro-Artemisinin–Piperaquine;

144 ***Some challenges***

145 A broader use of ivermectin to control malaria can pose several challenges including, potential
146 environmental contamination and effects on non-target organisms (37), withdrawal times in
147 livestock and implications milk or meat production (55), risk of inducing resistance in livestock
148 or human parasites (56–58) (59,60) (**Figure 1**).

149 Ivermectin is poorly metabolized in the human and animal body. Almost 80 to 98% of the
150 administered dose of ivermectin and/or its metabolites are excreted in the feces (61). The total
151 amount of ivermectin present in the environment will thus depend on the number of treated
152 human or livestock in an area, manure management and other agricultural practices. Repeated
153 MDA of ivermectin to humans and animals can pose a risk of contamination of freshwater
154 systems from agriculture or latrines through runoff, groundwater seepage or direct deposition
155 (62,63). Mosquito breeding sites could also be contaminated by ivermectin, exposing *Anopheles*
156 larvae to the drug (**Figure 1**). While some studies have shown that *Anopheles* larvae are
157 susceptible to ivermectin, repeated exposure of aquatic life stages to ivermectin could make
158 malaria vectors at adult stage less susceptible to ivermectin as it is the case for current
159 insecticides used both for agriculture and vector control (64,65). However, selection pressure of
160 ivermectin at larval stages may differ from the one caused by blood intake from ivermectin-
161 treated hosts. This may select for different resistance phenotypes, albeit this has not been
162 thoroughly investigated so far.

163 **Resistance to ivermectin in mosquitoes and other arthropods**

164 ***Theoretical framework of ivermectin resistance selection***

165 Random genetic mutations that occur during reproduction cause the offspring to vary in some
166 way from their parents (66). These changes that may be damaging can sometimes give an
167 advantage to an individual. A favorable mutation may increase an individual's chances of
168 surviving a harmful factor (*i.e.* drug, insecticide) long enough to reproduce and pass this new trait
169 on to its offspring. If the drug or insecticide is applied intensively and repeatedly, successive
170 populations will become less and less susceptible to the drug or insecticide. Individuals that are
171 not removed any more by the drug or insecticide used according to the label recommendation for
172 that individuals are referred to as "resistant or mutant".

173 Ivermectin is efficacious against most drug-naïve endoparasites at doses as low as 20 µg/kg body
174 weight (67), but doses of 150-200 µg/kg are needed to target the less susceptible parasites in its
175 spectrum/label, (the **dose-defining species**). This allows for an interesting phenomenon to occur
176 called the **window of scalation** in which the most susceptible species in the spectrum of the drug
177 could become resistant, requiring higher and higher concentration for its management, and yet
178 this would not be perceived until resistance has grown 10-fold (from 20 to 200 µg/kg) given that
179 the dose used was initially defined by the less susceptible species.

180 Resistance in livestock parasites (*i.e.* sheep, horses and cattle roundworms) has emerged shortly
181 after large scale, intensive use of ivermectin for veterinarian purposes (67,68). Surprisingly,
182 reports of resistance of ivermectin in arthropods remain scarce with only two ivermectin-resistant
183 arthropods (scabies mites and head lice) reported from human infestations in field situation
184 (69,70). In addition, despite over 30 years of ivermectin MDAs to control neglected tropical
185 diseases (NTDs) (71), no obvious evidence of resistance to ivermectin has been seen in
186 mosquitoes to date. Several factors could contribute to this: MDAs for NTDs are carried out only
187 once per year, only females are exposed to the drug in adult stage and ivermectin has a well

188 characterized impact in mosquito fertility (see window of selection below). This could have
189 avoided the development and spread of ivermectin resistance in mosquito populations, although
190 limited testing and the lack of a relevant surveillance system hinders the ability to draw
191 conclusions from this lack of evidence.

192 In mosquitoes, a favorable genetic mutation could appear on either a single individual or a
193 geographical area (*i.e.* a majority of mosquitoes in a village). The high concentration of
194 ivermectin in the treated hosts' (humans or animals) bloodstream last for a few days after
195 treatment killing both wild type and mutant mosquitoes. However, the effective concentration of
196 ivermectin declines rapidly after treatment (41,42). Mutant mosquitoes exposed to lower
197 concentrations could survive the exposure of ivermectin while the most susceptible ones are
198 killed. The period of time after treatment within which mutant individuals can thrive while the
199 susceptible ones are suppressed is termed the **window of selection** (72). The window of selection
200 of ivermectin opens when the concentration of the drug is low enough to allow mutant
201 individuals to reproduce but high enough to suppress the development of susceptible ones, and
202 closes once both mutant and susceptible individuals have equal survival probabilities (**Figure 2**).
203 Unlike insecticides used for IRS and on LLINs whose windows of selection continue to open for
204 many months or years (73), that of ivermectin is probably narrower, persisting only for a few
205 days or weeks, depending on the dose and/or formulation. Repetitive MDAs of ivermectin to
206 control malaria would theoretically increase the risk of selection by opening sequential windows
207 of selection, allowing resistant phenotype to amplify and be successfully passed onward.
208 However, ivermectin has the advantage of reducing not only the survival and fecundity of
209 exposed *Anopheles*, but also their locomotor activity (74). This may decrease the efficiency of
210 mating and blood-feeding, reducing the ability of mutant individuals to quickly amplify. Yet, it

211 does not bring the risk of emergence and spread of ivermectin resistance to zero since larvae,
 212 pupae and adult emergence have been reported (at low rates) in wild and laboratory *Anopheles*
 213 mosquitoes at a low concentration of ivermectin (75).

214 *Figure 2. Window of selection of ivermectin resistance in mosquitoes*

215 *Three doses of ivermectin are given 24 hours apart each. The efficacious concentration 50 (or*
216 *(Lethal Concentration 50, LC50) is 5ng/ml which kills 50% of An. gambiae in 5 days. Ivermectin*
217 *also precludes mosquito reproduction at lower concentrations. If a resistant type appears, there*
218 *will be a temporal gap between the concentration inhibiting the fecundity of the resistant and the*
219 *wild type. Stars indicate wild type (yellow) and mutant (red) 5 day-LC50, while crosses indicate*
220 *wild type (yellow) and mutant (red) concentrations allowing successful fecundity (concentration*
221 *unknown), (A). During the time the average ivermectin concentration is between these two*
222 *concentrations in the population, the resistant type can thrive while the susceptible type is*
223 *suppressed, (B). The window of selection is relatively narrow for ivermectin and mosquitoes,*
224 *particularly when one considers the potential concurrent presence of other vector control tools*
225 *such as LLINs and IRS, (C).*

226 ***Physiological resistance***

227 Numerous mechanisms has been associated with ivermectin resistance in arthropods including
228 reduced cuticular penetration in larvae (76) mutation of the targeted GluCl (70,77–80) and
229 metabolic through the overexpression of xenobiotic pumps (81–84) and cytochrome P450
230 isoenzymes (85–87).

231 The GluCl channel is the primary target of ivermectin in arthropods (88). In the malaria vector
232 *An. gambiae*, the alternative splicing process during gene expression that allows a single gene to
233 code for multiple proteins can lead to the production of ivermectin-sensitive or -insensitive
234 homomultimers (89). This suggests that resistance to ivermectin could arise through altered
235 regulation of the GluCl splicing in *An. gambiae* and probably in other *Anopheles* species as well.
236 Furthermore, metabolic resistance mechanisms (increased degradation and/or sequestration of the
237 insecticide by “detoxification” enzymes) drive an important proportion of pyrethroid and DDT

238 resistance in Africa (8,90). Dual inhibition of xenobiotic pumps and P450 cytochromes was also
239 found to greatly increase *An. gambiae* susceptibility to ivermectin, suggesting a clear pathway for
240 development of ivermectin resistance by detoxification mechanisms (87). Alarminglly,
241 permethrin-resistant cockroaches, houseflies, and *Aedes aegypti* have been shown to be less
242 susceptible to abamectin or ivermectin when compared with permethrin-sensitive counterparts
243 (91). Given the different target of both compounds (the GluCl channels for ivermectin and the
244 voltage-gated sodium channels for permethrin), this suggests that permethrin-ivermectin cross-
245 resistance could occur in mosquitoes through metabolic pathways involving P450 cytochromes
246 and/or xenobiotic pumps.

247 There are also some important facts to consider when studying resistance to ivermectin in
248 mosquitoes. The susceptibility to ivermectin varies widely through different *Anopheles* species,
249 (92) and with the development stage of mosquitoes (93) (43) (49). Also, mosquito larvae are
250 susceptible to ivermectin concentrations as low as 1 ng/ml and under (49). The potential exposure
251 to residual ivermectin in breeding sites and how it could affect resistance must be explored by
252 conducting targeted evolutionary experiments.

253 ***Behavioral resistance***

254 Beside target-site mutations and enhanced metabolic clearance, behavioral changes (*i.e.* trophic
255 avoidance) vis-a-vis to ivermectin-treated subjects could be an additional mechanism of
256 resistance. In fact, mosquitoes have the ability to identify the vertebrate host to be bitten through
257 a complex mixture of volatile molecules detected by their antenna (94–96). Drug metabolism has
258 also been shown to affect the body odor of treated individuals (97). While a change of body odor
259 is not reported among ivermectin's side effects, one cannot rule out the possibility of ivermectin
260 or its metabolites to modify the odor plume of treated subjects, making them attractive or

261 repulsive to *Anopheles* mosquitoes (**Figure 3**). A recent study has shown mosquitoes are capable
262 of associating the olfactory stimulus of pesticides with their detrimental effects and subsequently
263 avoid pesticide contact (98). This mechanism could enable mosquitoes to maximize survival in
264 environments becoming increasingly challenging owing to the intensification of chemical control
265 interventions.

266 An avoidance of ivermectin-treated subjects will cause mosquitoes to systematically feed on
267 untreated subjects such as pregnant women, children under 15kg, those taking contraindicated
268 drugs for co-administration (such as Ritonavir) and pregnant or milking cows in the case of
269 cattle. In addition, if ivermectin and LLINs are both widely implemented, it is probable that
270 mosquitoes may not be able to avoid contact with both current insecticides and ivermectin.

271 Insecticide resistance is shown to be associated with a high fitness cost on *Anopheles* populations
272 (delayed development of larvae, reduced survivorship of larvae and adults, reduced fecundity)
273 (99,100). Ivermectin is also known to affect mosquito survival and fecundity, and thus the ability
274 of exposed individuals to reproduce. To survive and perpetuate the species, mosquitoes could
275 adapt and limit their fitness loss following non-lethal exposure to insecticides and/or ivermectin
276 as found in other insect species through an increased reproductive effort (*i.e.* adjustment of egg
277 production) (101), thermoregulation (*i.e.* rest at some specific temperatures) (102,103) or self-
278 medication (*i.e.* feeding on specific therapeutic diets like nectars) (104,105). While these
279 behavioral changes are yet to be observed in mosquitoes, their occurrence would greatly
280 contribute to the spread of ivermectin resistance.

281

<p>Neutral (no effect): Ivermectin can be distributed to both humans and peri domestic animals</p>
<p>Attractive: The drug should only be distributed to peri domestic animals otherwise it will expose humans to more mosquito bites, thus to an increased risk of malaria</p>
<p>Repulsive: Untreated subjects (children under five years, women of childbearing age, pregnant women) will be exposed to more mosquito bites, thus to an increased risk of malaria. More protection should be offered to untreated subjects for this strategy to be ethically acceptable/appropriate.</p>

282

283 **Figure 3:** Schematic representation of the attractiveness or avoidance of ivermectin-treated hosts.

284 *The attractiveness of ivermectin-treated hosts to Anopheles mosquitoes could be studied using an*
 285 *olfactometer followed by a characterization of odorants using methods such as gas-*
 286 *chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry. These studies will determine if ivermectin-*
 287 *treated hosts are attractive (green arrow), repulsive (orange arrow) or neutral. The strategy to*
 288 *adopt for each scenario is described in the box.*

289 **Research and development agenda for ivermectin resistance management**

290 ***Characterization of cross-resistance to ivermectin***

291 Several reports and models have demonstrated the importance of ivermectin MDAs in disrupting
 292 the transmission of human malaria parasites (48,106,107). These encouraging data in favor of a
 293 wider use of ivermectin MDAs to combat malaria need however to be analyzed more in detail by
 294 taking into consideration factors that could limit or improve its use. Among factors that could
 295 limit the use of ivermectin is the occurrence of cross-resistance between current insecticides (*i.e.*
 296 pyrethroids) and ivermectin through metabolic resistance. Several of the randomized-controlled

297 field trials taking place are in the context of high levels of pyrethroid resistance (See **Table 1**).

298 Since some pyrethroid-resistant arthropods have been shown to be less susceptible to ivermectin

299 (91), conclusions that will be drawn from these trials should take into account potential limited

300 effect of ivermectin on mosquito populations with some degree of metabolic resistance. The

301 impact of pyrethroid resistance on ivermectin susceptibility in malaria vectors needs to be further

302 explored by assessing the effects of ivermectin on adult survival and fecundity using fully

303 susceptible and laboratory-selected permethrin resistant *Anopheles* strains for instance. As

304 overproduction of detoxifying enzymes are one of the main mechanisms by which insects survive

305 to insecticides, it will be critical to also characterize enzyme activity and mRNA expression

306 levels of cytochrome P450 and glutathione S-transferase (GST) genes between ivermectin-

307 sensitive and -insensitive pyrethroid-resistant *Anopheles* strains using both biochemical and high-

308 throughput genome sequencing assays as performed in crop insects (108–110).

309 The current strategy to combat metabolic-resistant malaria vectors is based on the use of LLINs

310 combining a pyrethroid with piperonyl butoxide (PBO); a synergist. Synergists or

311 chemosensitizers have been found to restore the toxicity or efficacy both in vivo and in vitro

312 when administered together with a toxicant or drug (111). Pyrethroid-PBO LLINs have been

313 shown to reduce malaria prevalence in areas where they were deployed compared to pyrethroid-

314 only LLINs (112,113). This has prompted the WHO to promote mass procurement and

315 distribution of these LLINs to sustain vector control impact in the face of increasing metabolic

316 resistance (114). Consequently, pyrethroid-PBO LLINs are rapidly replacing pyrethroid-only

317 LLINs in many malaria endemic areas. Their proportion in Sub-Saharan Africa is on the rise

318 going from 3% in 2018 to 51% in 2022 (115). This means that a deployment of ivermectin

319 MDAs will inevitably occur in communities where pyrethroid-PBO LLINs are already or will be

320 present. Since the PBO presents on these new generations of pyrethroid LLINs is intended to
321 inhibit detoxification enzymes of resistant malaria vectors, mainly cytochrome P450
322 monooxygenases (116), this might be beneficial for ivermectin MDAs. Indeed, the inhibition of
323 cytochrome P450 enzymes has been shown to increase the mortality of mosquitoes when the
324 synergist is co-administered with the blood meal (87). Even though mosquitoes will not be taking
325 a blood meal containing PBO, one could expect the pre or post exposure to PBO (through
326 pyrethroid-PBO LLINs) to synergize with ivermectin and increase mosquito mortality. Further
327 studies will be needed to investigate the potential role of a pre or post exposure to pyrethroid-
328 PBO LLINs in boosting ivermectin effects on mosquitoes since mosquito resistance to PBO-
329 synergized pyrethroid has already been reported (117).

330 *Development of standardized methods to track ivermectin resistance*

331 *Molecular markers*

332 Insecticide resistance in malaria vectors is clearly threatening current and future of vector control
333 programs. While waiting for large-scale implementation of new vector control products, it
334 appears essential to have a deep understanding of the mechanisms of insecticide resistance for
335 better detection in natural mosquito populations and management. Until today, our response to
336 this major problem has been reactive rather than proactive and understanding the molecular
337 mechanisms involved in resistance has often been limited by available techniques. Today,
338 advances in molecular biology offer new tools with significant potential for understanding and
339 tracking mosquito resistance to insecticides (118–120). These advances have also opened up the
340 potential for a more proactive approach when implementing new vector control tools such as
341 ivermectin MDA to control malaria. Before a large-scale use of ivermectin whatever the dose,
342 formulation and route of administration considered, it will be important to first establish

343 ivermectin resistant phenotypes selected under several generations at the laboratory with
344 increasing sub-lethal doses of ivermectin until resistance is observed. This could be done by
345 either exposing larvae or adult *Anopheles* to ivermectin. Establishment of ivermectin-resistant
346 *Anopheles* colonies is challenging because sub-lethal ivermectin concentrations can still inhibit
347 mosquito fecundity. Finding the optimal concentration (allowing survivors to lay eggs) will be
348 critical. If successful, the underlying mechanism(s) of the resistance can be investigated using
349 modern high-throughput genome sequencing (RNA- and/or DNA sequencing) and big data
350 analytics (**Figure 4**). These state-of-the-art techniques will give the ability to predetermine alleles
351 that are under selection and help identify potential markers of resistance (121). Markers of
352 ivermectin resistance could then be validated by genetic manipulation of candidate gene
353 expression in *An. gambiae s.l.* For example, RNAi-mediated gene silencing (122) can be used to
354 transiently suppress candidate gene expression in resistant mosquitoes prior to exposure to treated
355 blood meals with ivermectin. The GAL4/UAS expression system in *An. gambiae s.l.* (123,124)
356 can also be used to overexpress candidate genes in a susceptible mosquito population and
357 examine resistance phenotypes through exposure to treated blood meals with ivermectin. Another
358 promising tool for studies of gene function is the CRISPR-Cas9 system (125). This system allows
359 to alter the expression of a candidate gene and examine its impact on mosquito life traits such as
360 development, survival, fecundity/fertility, and ivermectin resistance can be tested. Once the
361 candidate gene or marker is validated, simplified molecular assays should be developed to track
362 ivermectin resistance in the malaria vectors as it is currently the case for mutations associated
363 with insecticide resistance on the voltage-gated sodium channel (VGSC) and
364 acetylcholinesterase-1 (Ace-1) genes in malaria vectors (8,120,126,127). Such an approach
365 before broader use of ivermectin will aid in the design of effective resistance-management
366 strategies and establish the impact of ivermectin resistance on malaria control interventions.

367

368 **Figure 4:** Ivermectin resistance marker discovery and validation pipeline. *The discovery of*
 369 *resistance markers starts with evidence of decreased sensitivity against ivermectin in laboratory-*
 370 *selected Anopheles populations. Genomic tools could then be used to identify resistance markers*
 371 *by comparison of parental and selected mosquito strains albeit with the known limitations in*
 372 *external validity of resistant colonies generated in the insectary. Validation of a resistance*
 373 *candidate is often performed using multiple in vitro and in vivo strategies (RNA interference,*
 374 *Gal4-UAS or CRISPR-Cas9), however the choice of organism may depend upon cost, timescale,*
 375 *and the availability of insect culturing facilities. After the validation of the resistance candidate*
 376 *by ivermectin bioassays, a molecular assay will be developed and validated to monitor*
 377 *ivermectin resistance in the field.*

378 ***Phenotypic assays***

379 In addition to molecular markers to track ivermectin resistance, the development of an effective
380 and easy-to-use phenotypic assay for resistance monitoring will provide a critical early warning
381 in areas where ivermectin MDA is under evaluation and after large scale implementation of this
382 strategy. Estimating the susceptibility of wild-caught adult mosquitoes to ivermectin requires
383 they ingest ivermectin in a blood meal or in sugar water either through a membrane or direct-
384 feeding on a treated host. Direct-feeding of mosquitoes on treated hosts has ethical implications
385 and membrane feeding often results in very low feeding rates. An alternative method using filter
386 papers to deliver ivermectin in blood is currently under development with promising results
387 (*Ominde et al, unpublished data*). Its use across different sites will require well-characterized
388 standard blood or sugar-blood mixture and the development of standard operating procedures
389 (SOPs) that will be applied to local F1 or F2 generation mosquitoes.

390 ***Ivermectin resistance mitigation plan***

391 There are several endectocides available in the veterinary market. This offers the possibility to
392 rotate or deliver a mosaic of different endectocides in herds as part of the livestock targeted
393 intervention. Mosaics could be done within herds or by using a different endectocide in an area
394 where humans receive ivermectin. The concept can be evaluated using ivermectin while
395 developing novel/improved endectocides' active pharmaceutical ingredients or formulations
396 specifically for malaria. Rotations will need at least two available endectocides for use in
397 humans. As for now, ivermectin remains the sole endectocide (with anti-mosquito properties)
398 approved for human use. One strategy could be the repurposing of alternative ectoparasitocidal
399 molecules such as Isoxazolines. Isoxazolines are ligand-gated ion channel inhibitor parasiticides.
400 They bind to gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)-gated chloride channels (GABACls) in nerve

401 and muscle cells, which blocks the transmission of neuronal signals leading to death. However,
402 their actions are putatively much more selective for GABA receptors in arthropods (fleas or
403 ticks), than for those in mammals, including humans (128,129). The current registered
404 Isoxazolines (Fluralaner and Afoxolaner) may be promising candidates for such a repurpose,
405 given the already demonstrated mosquitocidal activity against *Anopheles* at a relatively low
406 concentration, a much longer half-life in vivo (i.e. long time of residence) compared to
407 ivermectin, and the commercial availability of the drugs (130). However, seizures and other
408 neurotoxic effects, including death have been mentioned in some recently marketed isoxazoline
409 package inserts (131). It would therefore require an extensive work package to get an approval
410 human use. Further studies will be needed to calculate the optimal design of rotational treatment
411 in livestock or human that prevents the development and spread of ivermectin resistance in
412 malaria vectors.

413 Another approach could be the use of ivermectin in human or livestock in combination with a
414 synergist. This strategy is currently used to combat pyrethroid-resistant malaria vectors by
415 combining pyrethroids and PBO on LLINs (112,132). Cyclosporin A and Verapamil (ABC-
416 transporter inhibitors) have shown to cause an increase in the toxicity against ivermectin in cattle
417 tick, *Rhipicephalus microplus* (84,133,134) and in *Culex pipiens* mosquitoes (135). Similarly,
418 Voriconazole (Dual CYP/P-gp inhibitor) has a synergistic effect on ivermectin-induced *An.*
419 *gambiae* mortality (87). In the case of ivermectin, some synergist may simultaneously work as
420 pharmaco-enhancers, boosting both the systemic exposure and the mosquito susceptibility (136).
421 The use of synergists to increase the toxicity of ivermectin in mosquito populations could avoid
422 further selection of resistant malaria vectors and thereby delays the spread of ivermectin
423 resistance. Although all these drugs used as synergists have already been approved for human

424 use, their combination with ivermectin in livestock and humans will require extensive studies on
425 their pharmacokinetics and safety given their potential effect on the blood-brain barrier.

426 Additionally, attention must be paid to other potential uses that can increase the exposure and
427 hasten the appearance of resistance such as ivermectin-based sugar baits (137) or wall linings
428 (138).

429 **Concluding remarks**

430 Although there are numerous laboratory and field studies demonstrating the efficacy of
431 ivermectin for controlling malaria vectors, data from randomized-controlled field trials
432 demonstrating a direct impact of this strategy on malaria transmission are still awaited. So far,
433 only two published studies have examined the efficacy of repeated MDAs of ivermectin on the
434 incidence of malaria in a two-arm, cluster-randomized controlled trial (139,140). However, these
435 studies did not demonstrate a clear effect of ivermectin on malaria prevalence or transmission.
436 Preliminary data of the RIMDAMAL II project also showed no effect of ivermectin when added
437 to current malaria strategies (*Foy et al, unpublished data*). Several other trials are still ongoing
438 and will show us in years to come whether MDAs of ivermectin are effective or not for
439 controlling malaria.

440 On the meantime, it is critical to anticipate the research on ivermectin resistance in mosquitoes
441 (**see pending questions**) and identify effective resistance-management strategies in case this
442 strategy is evidenced as efficacious in controlling malaria. Molecular markers of ivermectin
443 resistance need to be identified and developed into validated assays as well as susceptibility tests
444 (phenotypic assays). However, the susceptibility of mosquitoes to ivermectin is species-
445 dependent, varying from 15.9 ng/ml (7-day LC₅₀) in *An. gambiae* (141) to much higher, 55.6

446 ng/ml (7-day LC_{50}) for *An. dirus* (51). Efforts to characterize major malaria vectors in different
447 geographic areas should be done prior to using ivermectin for vector control. In addition,
448 susceptibility tests should be validated from both colony and wild-type mosquitoes to determine
449 the dose-defining species, the dose that is needed to kill the less susceptible malaria vector. This
450 will not be achieved without first standardizing outcome metrics such as lethal concentration 50,
451 since a variety of time intervals are often presented varying from 24h to over 10 days.

452 **Pending questions**

- 453 • Ivermectin is delivered to the gut via the blood meal, how does this affect potential
454 resistance mechanisms? *i.e.* cuticular efflux pumps and pre-systemic metabolism
- 455 • How does the glutamate-gated chlorine channel expression vary across different mosquito
456 development stages and species?
- 457 • What is the window of selection of ivermectin and how does it vary across *Anopheles*
458 species?
- 459 • What is the most likely ivermectin resistance mechanism in mosquitoes?
- 460 • How will ivermectin resistance occur (and how fast) during or after the numerous
461 ivermectin trials in malaria vectors?
- 462 • What is the best way to monitoring ivermectin for resistance (SNPs, gene mutations,
463 phenotype assays) during trials?
- 464 • What is the ideal strategy combination to assess/prevent ivermectin resistance in
465 mosquitoes?

466 **Glossary**

467 **Anthropophilic:** Describes mosquitoes that prefer to take blood meals from humans

468 **Dose-defining species:** For antiparasitic drugs with a broad spectrum of activity like ivermectin,
469 the dose-defining species refers to the dose defined to target the parasite (herein an *Anopheles*
470 species) that requires the highest drug exposure to be suppressed.

471 **Endectocide:** A drug with a wide spectrum of activity capable of killing both endoparasites
472 (intestinal nematodes) and ectoparasites (blood-sucking insects)

473 **Endophagic:** An endophagic mosquito is a mosquito that feeds indoors, inside human habitats

474 **Endophilic:** An endophilic mosquito is a mosquito that tends to inhabit/rest indoors

475 **Exophagic:** An exophagic mosquito is a mosquito that feeds outdoors.

476 **Exophilic:** An exophilic mosquito tends to inhabit/rest outdoors.

477 **Residual malaria transmission:** Residual malaria transmission is the fraction of total
478 transmission that persists after achievement of full operational coverage with effective long-
479 lasting insecticidal nets and/or indoor residual spray interventions.

480 **Rotation:** If molecules with the same mode of action are used repeatedly, this will result in
481 increased selection pressure on an arthropod pest population, which enhances the rate (speed) of
482 resistance development. Endectocide rotation is the temporal (time) alternation of endectocides
483 with different modes of action to slow down the development of resistance.

484 **Self-medication:** the ability of insects to consume or otherwise contact biologically active
485 organic compounds specifically for the purpose of helping to reduce the deterrent effects of
486 insecticides.

487 **Synergist:** A chemical that enhances the effectiveness of an active agent

488 **Thermoregulation:** also known as temperature regulation, describes the ability of insects and
489 other animals to maintain a stable temperature (either above or below ambient temperature), at
490 least in a portion of their bodies by physiological or behavioral means.

491 **Window of escalation:** when the dose gap between the dose-defining species and the more
492 susceptible ones is large (e.g. for ivermectin 20 vs 200 mcg/kg), resistance arising in the most
493 susceptible organisms cannot be clinically detected until the intensity has risen to the level of the
494 highest dose (10-fold for ivermectin).

495 **Window of selection:** refers to time period during which the drug exposure is low enough to
496 allow mutant organisms to reproduce but high enough to suppress the development of wild-type
497 ones. This allows for amplification of the mutant phenotype.

498 **Zoophagic:** Describes mosquitoes that prefer to take blood meals from animals

499 **List of abbreviations**

500 **ABC-transporter:** Adenosine Triphosphate-Binding Cassette transporter

501 **Ace1:** Acetylcholinesterase 1

502 **CYP:** cytochrome P450

503 **DDT:** Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

504 **GABA:** Gamma-aminobutyric acid

505 **GAL4/UAS:** Gal4/upstream activating sequence

506 **GluCl:** Glutamate-gated chloride channel

507 **GST:** Glutathione S-Transferases

508 **IRS:** Insecticide Residual Spraying

509 **IVM:** Ivermectin

510 **LC:** Lethal Concentration

511 **LLIN:** Long-Lasting Insecticidal Nets

512 **MDA:** Mass Drug Administration

513 **NTD:** Neglected Tropical Diseases

514 **PBO:** Piperonyl butoxide

515 **P-gp:** P-glycoprotein

516 **VGSC:** Voltage-Gated Sodium Channel

517 **WHO:** World Health Organization

518 **Competing interests**

519 The authors declare no competing interests

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